

Table 1: Overall goal of primary studies.

Primary Study - Goal	Strategy	Procedure
[PS20] - Evaluate <i>Code Compose</i> , an internal AI-assisted coding system at Meta	Field Study	Survey (Open Ended feedback)
[PS25] - Case study of developing a business app through SDLC phases using systematic prompting	Experimental Simulation	Case study, Concept Implementation (Proof of Concept)
[PS27] - Evaluate an LLM-based tool for generating Ansible YAML code	Field Study	Survey
[PS9] - Compare novice coding with and without Copilot in terms of performance and experience	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment, Survey
[PS4] - Compare AI-pair and non-AI-pair projects in a mobile game studio	Field Study	Case study, Survey, Interviews
[PS6] - Investigates perceived productivity of GenAI integration in software development	Field Study	Case Study, Survey
[PS21] - Evaluates an IDE-integrated, prompt-less conversational LLM	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment: Within-subject, Survey
[PS3] - Investigate the impact of GenAI on labor productivity across domains	Sample Study	Survey
[PS2] - Modeling productivity and output quality of 70 large global companies using AI tools	Sample Study	Survey, Interview, Case Study
[PS28] - Measuring GitHub Copilot's impact on developer productivity for an automotive organization	Field Study	Case Study, Survey
[PS10] - Evaluate the benefits of using IDE auto-completion	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment: Between-subjects, Survey
[PS35] - Evaluate developers' performance with neural code translation	Laboratory Experiment	Case Study, Controlled experiment: Within-subjects, Survey
[PS36] - Investigate if code generation in PyCharm improves productivity	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment, Survey, Concept Implementation
[PS33] - Whether working with ChatGPT was helpful in coding and development tasks	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment: Between-groups, Survey
[PS34] - Explore how LLM-assistants impact productivity using the SPACE framework	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment: Within-subjects, Survey
[PS23] - Understand how access to Google Bard affects productivity and trust in coding	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment: Within-subjects, Survey
[PS13] - Gain insights into programmers' views on ChatGPT and other AI tools	Experimental Simulation	Survey
[PS16] - Compare performance of Stack Overflow vs. ChatGPT usage	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment: Between-groups, Survey
[PS32] - Compare highlighting conditions for AI code completion	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment: Within-subjects, Survey, Interview
[PS7] - Explore how professional developers perceive AI-based tools in their work	Field Study	Case Studies, Surveys
[PS14] - Comparing human-human vs. human-agent interaction using wizard-of-Oz	Laboratory Experiment	User Study, Interview, Survey
[PS5] - Compare novices' performance using ChatGPT vs. web search	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment, Survey
[PS18] - How LLMs affect students' learning and practice of software testing	Laboratory Experiment	Controlled experiment: Between-subjects, Survey

Primary Study - Goal	Strategy	Procedure
[PS17] - Understand developers' daily and continuous experiences with AI code assistants	Field Study	Interview
[PS15] - Understand developers' practices with AI tools to identify its benefits and challenges	Sample Study	Survey
[PS8] - Explore interaction patterns and challenges of using an AI tutor for students	Field Experiment	Concept Implementation, Surveys
[PS11] - Practical usefulness of ChatGPT for professional software engineers	Field Study	Observational Study, Survey
[PS22] - Initial experiences using a RAG-based coding LLM-assistant	Laboratory Experiment	User Study, Survey
[PS12] - Expert opinions on future GenAI impact on labor market	Judgment Study	Delphi Study, Interviews, Surveys
[PS26] - What influences engineers to adopt GenAI tools	Sample Study	Surveys
[PS37] - GitHub Copilot usage and self-reported productivity	Sample Study	Case Study, Survey
[PS19] - Understand how programmers interact with GitHub Copilot	Experimental Simulation	User Study, Survey
[PS30] - Prevent unhelpful prompts that affect software productivity	Laboratory Experiment	Concept Implementation (Proof of Concept)
[PS29] - Explore the role of bots on software development productivity	Formal Theory	-
[PS31] - Future of AI agents and programmers	Opinion Paper	-
[PS24] - Futuristic scenario on AI's impact on developers (2024–2030)	Opinion Paper	-
[PS1] - Roadmap of how AI reshapes software engineering	Formal Theory	-

Table 2: Study distribution across investigated *SPACE* dimension combinations.

SPACE Dimensions	Studies
Satisfaction	[PS7]
Performance	[PS3]
Communication	[PS1]
Activity + Efficiency	[PS10]
Performance + Activity	[PS30]
Performance + Efficiency	[PS2, PS12, PS25]
Satisfaction + Communication	[PS6, PS8, PS11]
Satisfaction + Efficiency	[PS15, PS17, PS22, PS26]
Satisfaction + Performance	[PS9, PS13, PS32, PS35]
Performance + Communication + Efficiency	[PS29]
Satisfaction + Activity + Efficiency	[PS27]
Satisfaction + Performance + Communication	[PS24]
Satisfaction + Communication + Efficiency	[PS21, PS31]
Satisfaction + Performance + Activity	[PS5, PS18, PS20]
Satisfaction + Performance + Efficiency	[PS4, PS16, PS23, PS33, PS36]
Satisfaction + Performance + Communication + Efficiency	[PS14]
All dimensions	[PS19, PS28, PS34, PS37]

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